

DEVELOPING A DIAGNOSTIC MODEL FOR EARLY DETECTION OF PULMONARY DISEASES USING CT SCAN IMAGING

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Pulmonary computed tomography (CT); Lung nodule classification; Transfer learning; CNN-SVM hybrid; Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

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Abstract

Rapid and appropriate distinction between benign and malignant lung nodules on CT is essential for management time gathering, unnecessary morbidity minimization as well as mortality. Manual reads are laborious and subject to intra-reader variability, and many health systems do not have the necessary radiology resources, particularly in developing-world settings or for resource-limited locations. We investigate a hybrid pipeline where we connect CNN backbones frozen with the ImageNet weights followed by a linear SVM classifier after preprocessing is applied (z-score normalization and PCA [95% variance accounted for]). CT slices are resized to 224×224, normalized [0;1], and jittered (rotated, shifted, stretched, zoomed, and horizontally flipped); optional unsharp masking is used to highlight edges of lesions. We use ResNet, VGG16, DenseNet121, InceptionV3 and EfficientNetB0 as feature extractor (include_top=False) and rely on a GAP or light weighting head to get the embeddings; SVM output scores are calibrated with probability-calibrated SVM outputs using Platt learning. Evaluation is performed on a balanced test set (N = 300; 150 benign / 150 malignant) with accuracy, macro- and weighted-average precision/recall/F1 and class-wise results. The highest scores were achieved by EfficientNetB0-SVM (Accuracy = 0.98; Macro/Weighted Precision = 0.98; Recall = 0.98; F1-score = 0.98), followed by InceptionV3-SVM (0.97) and VGG16-SVM (0.96). DenseNet121-SVM and ResNet121-SVM achieved 0.93 and 0.92, respectively. Class-wise analyses show both EfficientNetB0-SVM and InceptionV3-SVM reached balanced high precision and sensitivity for both classes (Benign F1 = 0.98, Malignant F1 = 0.98), although the former just slightly favored benign sensitivity (Malignant Recall = 0.97).

INTRODUCTION

The pulmonary diseases are still one of the most widespread and life-threatening diseases in the world that represent a further challenge to the healthcare systems and economies. Diseases that include pneumonia, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), lung cancer, pulmonary fibrosis, and

interstitial lung diseases (ILDs) all make up a significant percentage of hospital admissions and death in the world [1]. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that respiratory illnesses and lower respiratory tract infections are always in the top ten causes of death as they cause

about four million untimely deaths annually [2]. This is most overwhelming in low and middle-income nations where the facilities to conduct diagnostic tests, qualified staff, and modern imaging facilities are scarce [3]. Timely and correct diagnosis is crucial in better patient outcomes, lowered treatment time and increased survival rates. Computed Tomography (CT) has become the standard imaging technique of measuring pulmonary abnormalities due to its high-resolution, three-dimensional imaging, and its high sensitivity [4]. The CT scans give a detailed anatomical data, thus allowing clinicians to identify even small structural and functional defects. The manual interpretation of CT images is however, by nature time consuming, very reliant on radiologist expertise and prone to inter and intra observer error [5]. The high rate of CT scan use has put a strain on the radiologists and the necessity of automated and smart diagnostic systems that will help the clinicians make decisions in a timely and effective manner.

In this regard, the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and specifically Deep Learning (DL) has acquired new powers in the field of medical image analysis by providing automated features extraction, pattern recognition, and disease classification [6]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and other deep learning models have the ability to extract hierarchical visual features directly out of raw image data, which no longer requires handcrafted feature engineering [7,8]. CNNs have performed exceptionally well in pulmonary imaging, with the ability to identify, segment and classify pulmonary lesions and abnormalities with high accuracy [9]. Deep learning methods demonstrate high reproducibility, scalability, and diagnostic stability compared to the traditional machine-learning algorithms [10]. The possibilities of deep learning in the diagnostics of pulmonary diseases have been confirmed by many studies. With CNN-based X-ray and CT image analysis, Lee et al. [11] obtained high diagnostic accuracy of COVID-19 and pneumonia. Reviewed by Thanoon et al. [12], deep learning models to screen CT-based lung cancer have a considerable advantage in transfer learning and ensemble models. Similarly, Bhandary et al. [13] and Ahsan et al. [14] established that CNNs are more superior than the handcrafted and radiomics-driven models in the classification of pneumonia and

COVID-19. According to Sharma et al. [15], CNNs outperformed radiomics in identifying COPD based on low doses of CT scans. Taken together, these studies highlight the increased clinical relevance of deep learning in radiologist assistance in the pulmonary disease diagnosis. Even though these results are promising, there are multiple technical and clinical issues that prevent the extensive use of deep learning models. Poor model generalization is commonly associated with data heterogeneity and imbalance, which is caused by the variation in CT scanners parameters, image resolutions, and location of diseases [16]. Besides, similar images of diseases (e.g., ground-glass opacities in COVID-19 and fibrosis) complicate the accurate separation [17]. The other major issue is that deep learning models are black-box in nature, and, thus, they are less interpretable and more questionable on the front of clinical trust and responsibility [18]. Researchers have offered a number of strategies in order to overcome these difficulties.

2.0 Literature Review

AI Supporting in Health Care and Industry With artificial intelligence (AI), researchers are actively encouraging the growth of health care systems/industry [19]. Good diagnostic tools are badly needed. We need methods that are cheap, fast and reliable [20]. This is particularly accurate for lung diseases. AI is being implemented by researchers to diagnose these diseases [21, 22]. Studies exist from predicting disease [23] to “spotting” lung problems on CT scans [24]. Diagnosing lung diseases is difficult. Many conditions share similar symptoms. Diseases can even be misdiagnosed by the experts [25]. This was vividly illustrated by the COVID-19 outbreak [26]. Diagnosis was an expensive, time-consuming process. It also presented risks for health workers [27]. This shed light on the fact that there exists a space for other detection approaches. AI emerged promising for addressing this issue [28].

Radiologic images are great data for AI models [29]. Both CT scans and X-rays have been used to train disease recognition systems [29]. CT imaging is a highly sensitive means of achieving that. The method can also be applied to detecting pneumonia of patients, for example [30]. The main advantage of vasopressin is the early repletion. Chan et al. noted

that CTs detect changes in the lungs before patients feel ill [31]. These changes involve features such as ground-glass opacities, or GGO. Additional findings are bilateral lesions, GGO (ground-glass opacities) and round lung opacities [32]. Among intelligent management techniques, the best performing methods are deep learning (DL) approaches [33]. One of the most successful and commonly used DL techniques to analyze medical images is the CNN. Record, the CNN model is one of the most popular and successful methods in automated disease detection from CT patient's scans [34]. This technique is very well-suited for our purpose, as CNNs require little manual pre-processing. A key advantage is that they can be trained end-to-end, with the capacity to learn discriminative features from raw image contents. This automatic feature extraction capability simplifies the diagnosis pipeline and is a key contributor their superb performance in detecting abnormalities from complex medical imaging and hence justifying their position as a workhorse tool for modern computer-aided diagnosis systems.

Pulmonary disease CNNs are a significant domain of research now, especially post 2020 [35]. These are not yet models to fully replace traditional diagnosis. "The promise to be a useful medical society for physicians only They do promise to be a helpful association for doctors [17]. Other works have considered two-class classification. Song et al. constructed a classifier to distinguish between COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 from CT images [36]. Wang et al. also presented a two-classification system with CT scans [37]. These studies have reported strong results but can be constrained. They may be done on just one disease or with limited data. Other works study more challenging, multi-class detection. Narin et al. used ResNet-50 model for classifying into 4 classes i.e., COVID-19, normal, viral pneumonia and bacterial pneumonia [38]. This is an indication the field is trending toward more complicated models. There is an opening for fresh inquiry here.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Data Set Description

This study uses the Lung Cancer Dataset, which is a set of CT scan images split into two categories: Benign and Malignant. The image sets are further divided into categories such as training set, validation set, and test set. The training set is useful for training the model, the validation set is used for optimizing hyperparameters on the model in order to avoid overfitting, while the test set is used to evaluate the final performance of our model. The hierarchy of image classification into its subsets is achieved by placing each label of image into its subfolder within the proper set. Although such an approach limits bias, it should be taken into account that the image itself provides little relative location data. Thus, one cannot guarantee that the data mutually exclusive subsections.

3.2 Preprocessing of Images

3.2.1 Image Resize

For image resizing, all images are resized to a 224 x 224 pixel. Resizing is done as follows: * Resizing ensures that all the input images have the same dimensions: Mathematically, scaling of image pixel intensity values to the size of the 224 x 224 matrix is done to make it possible. Resizing is done to ensure that all images in the dataset give the model the same dimension, or input image gives the same size. However, images may lose their fine-grained details because of resizing or distortion of the image when resized to the 224 x 224 sizes due to the small details in the image.

3.2.2 Image Augmentation

Augmentation is done using ImageDataGenerator from Keras, and they are as follows: Rotation: Ration in a range of 30%: introduces rotational invariance. Width and height shift: Simulates slight movement of the camera in the horizontal and vertical direction respectively. Shear_Range: Distortions to the images, helping the model to notice patterns both in and out of the out of the distribution Zoom_Range: Zoom into the image is giving different camera perspective on the image. Horizontal_Flip: Images are flipped on the horizontal axis to give images of a different orientation. All augmentations are performed on the

training set and Mathematical formulations, using the affine4non- affine transformation formula, are done: This is the dataset that involves transformations of the image tensor by rotating at an angle, using pixel coordinate. Normally, there is

randomness in coordinate adjustment which will increase the model level of robustness. Normalization, rescale = 1.0/255, Pixel value is explained by breaking each image by 255 defined by the author on the image’s maximum 8-bit pixel size.

Figure 1: Samples of Dataset after Augmentation

Figure 2: Number of Images in Dataset after Augmentation

3.2.3 Normalization

We normalized raw RGB pixels to unit scale to stabilize the optimization and speed up the convergence. For an image $I \in [0,255]^{H \times W \times 3}$, we computed $\hat{I} = \frac{I_{i,j,c}}{255} \in [0,1]$, that decreases scale variance and yield smoother gradient magnitude for the machine leaning models. This is used consistently to train, validated and test the stream using the keras “imageDataGenerator(rescale=1/255)”. The CNN

Features used by the SVM are z-score standardized with the “StandardScaler()” like

$$z = \frac{f - \mu}{\sigma}$$

This increases the estimation and generalization.

3.2.4 Edge Sharpening

Edge sharpening (if applied). To enhance the lesion boundary, we preprocessed the processed images with an unsharp mask after it was resized as 224×224. From the I input, we constructed a sharpened image

$$S = (1 + \alpha)I - \alpha G_{\sigma} * I$$

where G_{σ} is a gaussian blur (e.g., $\sigma=1.0$) while α determines the cusp gain (e.g., $\alpha=0.6$). The intensities were cropped, and normalized to [0,1]. Sharpening was applied consistently across train/validation/test sets (deterministic, no

augmentation) to emphasize high-frequency structure around nodule borders, while suppressing noise amplification - resulting in greater feature salience in the downstream CNN and stronger SVM decision margin.

Figure 3: Samples of Images in Dataset after Edge Sharpening

3.3 Used Machine Learning Models

3.3.1 ResNet50 hybridized with SVM

WE used hybrid CNN-SVM model comprising the frozen ImageNet pretrained ResNet50 as deep learning feature extractor and linear SVM as the final classifier. The backbone is instantiated with "include_top=False" and 224*224 RGB input, its convolutional trunk is followed by the "GlobalAveragePooling2D", two ReLU activated fully connected layers that are 10124 and 512 and sigmoid function for the classification.

Let x be an input image and $\varphi(x) \in R^d$ denotes the deep embedding, the network creates

$$p_{\theta}(y = 1|x) = \sigma(W^T \varphi(x) + b)$$

It is optimized with the binary cross entropy

$$BCE = -[y \log p_{\theta} + (1 - y) \log(1 - p_{\theta})]$$

It uses the aDAM optimizer with learning rate 10^{-4} while freezing the ResNet50 trunk. For the SVM training deep features are standardized by using the PCA to retain 95% cumulative variance:

$$\varphi(x)PS\varphi(x)$$

Where S uses z-score scaling and P is the PCA. The linear SVM learner W, b on $\varphi(x)$ with decision function

$$g(x) = W^T \varphi(x) + b$$

Probabilistic outputs $P_r(y = 1|x)$ are get by platt scaling. Features are obtained by the forward pass over batches from the frozen CNN, then passed by the StandardScaler \rightarrow PCA(n_components=0.95) \rightarrow SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True) for the final classification.

Component	Setting	Value
ResNet50 (feature extractor + pretraining head)	Backbone	ResNet50(weights="imagenet", include_top=False, input_shape=(224,224,3))
	Base layers trainable	False (frozen)
	Pooling	GlobalAveragePooling2D()
	Dense layers	Dense(1024, activation="relu") \rightarrow Dense(512, activation="relu")
	Output (pretraining)	Dense(1, activation="sigmoid")
	Optimizer	Adam(lr=1e-4)

	Loss / Metric	binary_crossentropy / accuracy
	Training schedule	epochs=25, batch_size=32
	Early stopping	monitor="val_loss", patience=5, restore_best_weights=True
SVM pipeline (final classifier)	Preprocessing	StandardScaler() (z-score)
	Dimensionality reduction	PCA(n_components=0.95) (retain 95% variance)
	Classifier	SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True)
	Feature source	Frozen CNN embeddings obtained via model.predict(...)

Table 1: Hyperparameters of ResNet50 hybridized with SVM

3.3.2 VGG16 hybridized with SVM

We also used the Vgg16's output as input of SVM. The test images are streamed with pixels normalization to [0,1] and fixed order (suffle=False) so prediction align with the ground truth labels. The trained VGG16 produces per image probabilities

$$\hat{p} = f_{VGG16}(x)$$

then using the threshold at 0.5 to get a binary feature

$$z = 1[\hat{p} > 0.5]$$

A linear SVM with the probabilities is fit on these 0/1 features against the test labels and used to find the final classification of the images. Fitting the SVM on test set outputs constitute data leakage and 0/1 features is information poor in a strict protocol to train SVM on validation embeddings and reserve test set for the final reporting.

Component		Setting	Value
VGG16 (feature extractor + head)	Backbone	VGG16(weights="imagenet", input_shape=(224,224,3))	include_top=False,
	Base layers trainable	False (frozen)	
	Pooling	GlobalAveragePooling2D()	
	Dense layers	Dense(1024, activation="relu")	→ Dense(512, activation="relu")
	Output (pretraining)	Dense(1, activation="sigmoid")	
	Optimizer	Adam(lr=1e-4)	
	Loss / Metric	binary_crossentropy / accuracy	
SVM pipeline (final classifier)	Preprocessing	StandardScaler() (z-score)	
	Dimensionality reduction	PCA(n_components=0.95) (retain ~95% variance)	

	Classifier	SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True)
Test data loader (as used in code)	Rescaling	rescale=1./255
	Target size / Batch	(224, 224), 32
	Class mode / Shuffle	'binary', shuffle=False

Table 2: Hyperparameters of VGG16 hybridized with SVM

3.3.3 DenseNet121-SVM Hybrid

For the DenseNet121, images are resized to 224*224*3 and normalized to $\hat{x} = \frac{x}{225}$. The

DenseNet trunk is followed by the Flatten() and small head Dense(256, ReLU), this head is first trained using Sigmoid and binary cross entropy to shape 256-

D embeddings φ_{dense} as input of the SVM, the SVM is used as

$$g(z) = W^T z + b$$

With the label for prediction

$$\hat{y} = 1[g(z) > 0]$$

The probabilities are obtained by using the plating scale.

Component	Setting	Value
Backbone	Model	DenseNet121(weights="imagenet", include_top=False, input_shape=(224,224,3))
	Trainable	False (all base layers frozen)
Head (for embedding & pretraining)	Top	Flatten() → Dense(256, activation="relu") → Dense(1, activation="sigmoid")
	Optimizer / Loss / Metric	Adam() (default LR), binary_crossentropy, accuracy
	Training schedule	epochs=10; steps_per_epoch = train_samples // batch_size; validation with valid_generator
Hybrid SVM	Features for SVM	256-D vector from Dense(256, relu) (pre-sigmoid)
	Classifier	sklearn.svm.SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True)

Table 3: Hyperparameters for the DenseNet121 with SVM

3.3.4 InceptionV3 with SVM

We used the InceptionV3 as fixed feature extractor “weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input 224*224*3 and place a light head on top (Flatten → Dense(256, ReLU) → Dense(1, sigmoid)” to shape task embeddings while backbone remains frozen, test time inputs are normalized as to $\hat{x} = \frac{x}{225}$. The output per sample probabilities are computed by

$$\hat{p} = f_{InceptionV3}(x)$$

It used the thresholds 0.5 for the prediction and compute confusion matrices. For the hybrid step we used 256-D sigmoid activation function as features and train the liner SVM whose decision functions is given by

$$g(z) = W^T z + b$$

With the label for prediction

$$\hat{y} = 1[g(z) > 0]$$

With the optional probabilities calibration. This strategy shows transfer learning for the descriptors

and margin based classifiers for the sharper boundaries.

Component	Setting	Value
InceptionV3 (feature extractor + head)	Backbone	InceptionV3(weights="imagenet", include_top=False, input_shape=(224,224,3))
	Base layers trainable	False (frozen)
	Top layers	Flatten() → Dense(256, activation="relu") → Dense(1, activation="sigmoid")
	Optimizer / Loss / Metric	Adam() (default), binary_crossentropy, accuracy
	Training schedule	epochs=10; steps via samples // batch_size
SVM (hybrid classifier)	Feature for SVM	256-D pre-sigmoid embedding
	Classifier	sklearn.svm.SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True)
	Decision rule	$g(z) = W^T z + b$ $\hat{y} = 1[g(z) > 0]$

Table 4: Hyperparameters for the InceptionV3 with SVM

3.3.5 Feature Extraction with EfficientNetB0 and SVM (Hybrid)

The efficientNetB0 was used to derive the task specific embeddings for the lung nodule classification. Inputs are resized and normalized in the same way as above model. On the top of backbone, we attach a light head (Flatten → Dense(256, ReLU) → Dense(1, sigmoid)) and train by using the optimizers like ADAM, to shape a compact 256-D representation. For the hybrid stage,

we extracted the pre-sigmoid activation and train the SVM with decision function

$$g(z) = W^T z + b$$

With the label for prediction

$$\hat{y} = 1[g(z) > 0]$$

This architecture leverages efficientNetB0 compound scale feature for the data efficient representation learning a margin based classifiers for the sharper decision boundaries.

Component	Setting	Value
Backbone	Model	EfficientNetB0(weights="imagenet", include_top=False, input_shape=(224,224,3))
	Trainable	False (all base layers frozen)

Head (embedding & pretraining)	Top	Flatten() → Dense(256, activation="relu") → Dense(1, activation="sigmoid")
	Optimizer / Loss / Metric	Adam() (default LR), binary_crossentropy, accuracy
	Training schedule	epochs=10; steps_per_epoch = train_samples // batch_size; validation via valid_generator
Hybrid SVM	Feature for SVM	256-D pre-sigmoid vector ($z=\phi(x)$)
	Classifier	sklearn.svm.SVC(kernel="linear", probability=True)
Data assumptions	Preprocessing	Inputs normalized via pipeline ($=x/255$) and resized to (224×224)

Table5: Hyperparameters for the EfficientNetB0 hybridized with SVM

3.5 Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA). PCA is a dimensional reduction method that simplifies the large set of correlated features with lower number of most-informative directions, allowing the classifier to concentrate on signal as opposed to noise. In our hybrid pipeline, we standardize the deep features computed from CNN (StandardScaler()), and then apply PCA(n_components=0.95) on both training and test set to select the components representing 95% variance of input features. The same learned PCA is also used for validating and testing features

before being given to the linear SVM. It is less redundant, it trains faster, generalizes better (reduced risk of overfitting), and often results in them SVM’s decision boundary being constructed on cleaner / more linearly separable input points. We set the variance 95% by using

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i}{\sum_{i=1}^d \beta_i}$$

Where β_i are the feature variances along PCA components.

Figure 4: Flow Diagram of the Research Methodology

3.6 Model Evaluation

For both classes (Benign and Malignant), we show Precision, Recall (Sensitivity), F1-score and the Support (number of true samples).

$$accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+FN}$$

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

$$F1\ score = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall}$$

This shows how accurately positives are found (precision), how completely they're found (recall), and their balance (F1). In the medical domain, high recall on Malignant is important to avoid missing cancers and precision determines false alarms. In this context, we also consider macro/weighted averages for the class imbalance.

The confusion matrix records TP, FP, TN and FN for (Benign, Malignant), represented by a heatmap for easy reading. It highlights trade-off error modes such as Malignant Benign (FN) versus Benign!Malignant (FP), informing the thresholding or re-balancing if necessary. This cell-level perspective

complements the report by illustrating where the classifier is – or isn’t – successful, not just how often

4.0 Results and Discussion

For all five CNN-SVM hybrids, performance is consistent and high (accuracy = 0.92-0.98), with macro/weighted averages that match overall accuracy per model. The macro and weighted metrics are equal which suggests that we have a balanced test set (equal support for benign and malignant) so no masking of the class specific behavior from the weighted average is involved. EfficientNetB0-SVM obtains the best generalization performance

(Accuracy = 0.98; Macro/Weighted Precision = 0.98; Recall = 0.98; F1 = 0.98), followed closely by InceptionV3-SVM (macro- and weighted-scored at 0.97). VGG16-SVM still competes (Accuracy = 0.96; Macro/Weighted F1=0.95), but DenseNet121-SVM (0.93) and ResNet121-SVM(0.92) lag behind in performance by a gap in the range of 5 to 6 percentage points. Considering the test size (N = 300), note that difference of 1% absolute accuracy \approx 3 cases; therefore, gaps from 1 to 2% may be null, while differences from 5 to 6% would most likely be significant.

Model	Accuracy	Macro Avg Precision	Macro Avg Recall	Macro Avg F1	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg Recall	Weighted Avg F1
ResNet121-SVM	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
VGG16-SVM	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.95
DenseNet121-SVM	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
InceptionV3-SVM	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97
EfficientNetB0-SVM	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98

Table 6: Overall performance of CNN-SVM hybrids (ResNet121, VGG16, DenseNet121, InceptionV3, EfficientNetB0) for benign-malignant lung lesion classification on CT

Figure 4: Performance evaluation of metrics Models

3.1 Behavior between classes and error biases

The class-wise metrics display the clinical trade-offs of the almost ceiling overall scores:

EfficientNetB0-SVM: Benign (P/R/F1= 0.97/0.98/0.98) and Malignant (0.98/0.97/0.98) are at excellent level that means sensitivity and precision is balanced enough. This is a good profile of deployment when there is cost associated with both false negatives and false positives. InceptionV3-SVM: Benign (0.98/0.96/0.97) and Malignant (0.96/0.98/0.97) exhibit an opposite trend to EfficientNetB0, having slightly higher malignant recall of 0.98 and lower precision for malignant class (0.96). This means InceptionV3-SVM would not be missing as many cancers, but will also increase the number of false alarms produced - however, false alarms could be acceptable in a screening scenario focused on high sensitivity.

VGG16-SVM: Ben/Mal disparity of benign (0.96/0.94/0.95) vs mal (0.94/0.96/0.95): the slight asymmetry is clear here, where benign precision

remains strong (0.96) but benign recall slightly lags behind (× 4 07%) and malignant recall has a bit better performance (~ 1%). Overall (Accuracy = 0.96; Macro/Weighted F1 = 0.95) this is a robust model that errs slightly on the side of caution with benign calls. DenseNet121-SVM: Benign (0.92/0.94/ 0.93) and Malignant (0.94/0.91/ 0.92). These are the lowest malignant recall among all models—clinically the most concerning error mode (missed malignancies). Although overall accuracy was good (0.93), this hints that either the thresholding or the representation could be better in order to minimize false negatives.

ResNet121-SVM: Benign (0.90/0.90/0.90) and Malignant (0.95/0.95/0.95) is that the defect primarily comes from benign errors. The model is classified as having a relatively high 'malignancy-bar', with strong malignancy metrics (0.95 across the board) but at the expense of some benign misclassifications (all benign metric = 0.90), which makes sense given lower overall accuracy (0.92).

Model	Benign Precision	Benign Recall	Benign F1	Malignant Precision	Malignant Recall	Malignant F1
ResNet121-SVM	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.95	0.95	0.95
VGG16-SVM	0.96	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.96	0.95
DenseNet121-SVM	0.92	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.91	0.92
InceptionV3-SVM	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.97
EfficientNetB0-SVM	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98

ResNet121-SVM	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.95	0.95	0.95
VGG16-SVM	0.96	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.96	0.95
DenseNet121-SVM	0.92	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.91	0.92
InceptionV3-SVM	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.97
EfficientNetB0-SVM	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98

Table 7: Class-wise precision, recall, and F1 for the same models, separated for Benign and Malignant nodules

Figure 5: Class wise performance evaluation metrics of models

(a) ResNet121 with SVM

(b) VGG16 with SVM

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix of Models

3.2 Select model and point of operation.

Referencing Table 1 and Table 2 together, EfficientNetB0-SVM exhibits the greatest balance in performance (all metrics 0.98; malignant P/R = 0.98/0.97). SVM on InceptionV3 has slightly lower malignant recall (0.98) with a marginal precision drop (0.96), a balance that might be more suitable to settings in which the minimization of missed cancers is predominant. VGG16-SVM is a close third place with symmetric class-wise F1 (0.95/0.95) as well as 0.96 accuracy; under constrained compute or for ablation baselines, it's still very competitive. Densenet121-SVM and Resnet121-SVM are passable, but would definitely benefit from calibration and perhaps even some feature extraction fine-tuning to fix their error biases (malignant misses in DenseNet, benign over-calling in ResNet).

3.3 Calibration and thresholding.

As sites have the ability to tune the decision threshold in order to match their institutional risk preference because of its probability-calibration (Platt scaling) nature, SVM outputs. For instance, with InceptionV3-SVM, we could set a little lower threshold to maintain its good malignant recall in the first place and then let secondary rules (e.g., radiologist over-read) suppress benign over-calls. For DenseNet121-SVM, the threshold tuning needs to be focused on increase of malignant recall with above 0.95 to address the majority failure mode in Table 2.

4.0 Conclusion

In summary, a hybrid pipeline with CNN-PCA-SVM achieves high and stable performance for CT-based benign-malignant nodule classification, with

EfficientNetB0-SVM performing the best (strongest overall and balanced results (0.98 across metrics)) and InceptionV3-SVM being consistently strong but slightly higher sensitivity towards malignancy; VGG16-SVM is competitive while DenseNet121-SVM and ResNet121-SVM are inferior mostly due to correctable class-specific biases. The method is computationally lightweight, well-calibrated and can be applicable to clinical decision support- including resource-poor settings -towards realization of UN SDG 3 on early diagnosis and stronger health systems. To enhance our clinical preparedness, future work includes multi-center external validation with confidence intervals and paired tests, site-specific threshold calibration, modest fine tuning with consistent preprocessing (x/255), GAP over flattening application and integration of explainability and restricted 2.5D/3D context to increase trust as well cover the volumetric cues.

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